

Boulder Petroglyphs Photogrammetry

Processing Report

Data collected with Skydio 2+ drone using 3D Scan app on 10/26/2022 by the Center for Advanced Spatial Technologies, University of Arkansas, in collaboration with the Oklahoma Archeological Survey, University of Oklahoma.

02 February 2023

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	129	Camera stations:	129
Flying altitude:	3.22 m	Tie points:	36,311
Ground resolution:	1.53 mm/pix	Projections:	94,696
Coverage area:	254 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.457 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
2+ (3.7mm)	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

2+ (3.7mm)

129 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	4056 x 3040	3.7 mm	1.5 x 1.5 μm

	Value	Error	F	Cx	Cy	B1	B2	K1	K2	K3	P1	P2
F	2427.93	0.16	1.00	0.09	-0.52	-0.12	-0.05	0.07	0.15	-0.16	0.08	-0.50
Cx	14.0182	0.17		1.00	-0.03	0.11	-0.02	0.01	-0.01	0.02	0.90	0.01
Cy	-13.7972	0.19			1.00	-0.07	-0.04	-0.13	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.89
B1	-28.0108	0.072				1.00	0.04	-0.06	-0.02	0.02	0.15	0.13
B2	0.901486	0.046					1.00	-0.01	0.01	-0.00	-0.10	0.07
K1	-0.000750035	0.00012						1.00	-0.92	0.84	0.03	-0.13
K2	0.00404159	0.00027							1.00	-0.98	-0.02	0.01
K3	-0.00765799	0.00019								1.00	0.03	0.01
P1	-9.76131e-06	2e-05									1.00	0.02
P2	-0.000116578	2.1e-05										1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
28.8828	36.0902	65.3694	46.2247	80.0617

Table 3. Average camera location error.

X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated GCP locations are marked with a dot or crossing.

Count	X error (μm)	Y error (μm)	Z error (μm)	XY error (μm)	Total (μm)
7	0.100664	0.0555732	0.0472904	0.114985	0.12433

Table 4. Check points RMSE.

X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (μm)	Y error (μm)	Z error (μm)	Total (μm)	Image (pix)
point 1	-0.253029	0.139658	-0.122219	0.313792	0.000 (3)
point 2	0.0211368	0.0081677	-0.00234002	0.0227805	0.000 (15)
point 3	-0.0238417	0.00319844	0.0104689	0.0262345	0.000 (33)
point 4	0.0673455	-0.0190224	-0.015768	0.0717349	0.000 (13)
point 5	0.00340928	0.0373419	0.0115485	0.0392352	0.000 (23)
point 6	-0.0332878	0.0165151	-0.012668	0.0392594	0.000 (31)
point 7	0.0154407	-0.002894	0.00772385	0.0175057	0.000 (38)
Total	0.100664	0.0555732	0.0472904	0.12433	0.000

Table 5. Check points.
X - Longitude, Y - Latitude, Z - Altitude.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 1.07 cm/pix
Point density: 0.874 points/cm²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	129
Aligned cameras	129
Markers	7
Coordinate system	WGS 84 (EPSG::4326)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Point Cloud

Points	36,311 of 141,115
RMS reprojection error	0.182416 (0.456666 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.606648 (2.55987 pix)
Mean key point size	2.42571 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	3.89876

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	High
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	Source
Key point limit	40,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Exclude stationary tie points	No
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	3 minutes 34 seconds
Matching memory usage	870.10 MB
Alignment time	1 minutes 31 seconds
Alignment memory usage	146.57 MB

Optimization parameters

Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k3, p1, p2
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Optimization time	1 seconds
Date created	2022:10:27 02:47:37
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	9.65 MB

Depth Maps

Count	123
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Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	Medium
Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	3 minutes 43 seconds
Memory usage	620.23 MB
Date created	2022:10:27 03:01:16
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	109.58 MB

Dense Point Cloud

Points	8,310,943
Point colors	3 bands, uint8

Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	Medium
Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	3 minutes 43 seconds
Memory usage	620.23 MB
Dense cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	6 minutes 56 seconds
Memory usage	2.04 GB
Date created	2022:10:27 03:08:12
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	121.28 MB
Model	
Faces	1,992,750
Vertices	997,049
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, 4 bands, uint8
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	Medium
Filtering mode	Moderate
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	3 minutes 43 seconds
Memory usage	620.23 MB
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	3 minutes 49 seconds
Memory usage	2.60 GB
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	3 minutes 3 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	2.87 GB
Blending time	3 minutes 21 seconds
Blending memory usage	1.72 GB
Blending GPU memory usage	869.48 MB
Date created	2022:10:27 03:25:52
Software version	1.8.0.13794
File size	115.98 MB
System	
Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	1.8.0 build 13794
OS	Windows 64 bit
RAM	31.85 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-6920HQ CPU @ 2.90GHz
GPU(s)	Quadro M2200